

E- Regional Transport System

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outsourcing have induced transport and logistics companies to look for different ways to grow and improve their competitive advantage[1]. For each type of transport we need their license. Their different categories in which we can take our license. Also most of the people today work for longer hours and do not have the flexibility to take a break from work to give the licenses tests. People have not spent more time for licenses test. So with the help of Electronic RTO system we can quickly give our mock test and get result from it. It helps us to prepare for license test. The People want a facility where they can have easy to issue their licenses. The facility to achieve schedule date by SMS, call or mail. The people collect their license from post and travel from long distance for issuing license. So, the people waste their money.

Roadside barriers, including the noise barriers and trees along the road, can also affect the dispersion of the particles[3]. So if we better know about the traffic and roadway rules we can easily eliminate or reduce this type of barriers. Like now a day government starts checking mono-carbon of all vehicles by pollution test machine. It helps us to make earth less polluted by the pollution generated by vehicles. Although many studies focus on the dispersion of vehicle exhausts, the influence of vehicle emitted particles on the indoor air quality near the roadway is rarely mentioned, and some debates exist on the mitigation effect of the roadside barrier[3].

Abstract

In today's world with the increasing traffic and longer commuting distances it is becoming very difficult. Also most of the people today work for longer hours and do not have the flexibility to take a break from work. To proper management of the roadway and city traffic we need some rule and category. The RTO system provide us that rule in the terms of license and following all the certain rules we can break the difficulty level of traffic. This paper describe about current RTO system and different test conduct for the vehicle license.

Keywords: traffic, license, transport.

1. Introduction

In today's world with the increasing traffic and longer commuting distances it is becoming very difficult for people to travel for their particular licenses issue. Transport is a major factor for any industry and business. It offers industries to transport their products by various ways. Competition and opportunities in the era of global trade, investment and

1.1 OBJECTIVE

Now a day it is require to build new Website according to RTO office infrastructure and Facilities. So that all the people can get information about the e-RTO. By this project we can create a web application to be used in place of old system. In this project we are using ASP.NET and SQL Server technology to create strong and secured database connectivity. We can also maintain and improve the skill management for the department personnel and ensure transparency in the day-to-day management and administration of the officials.

1.2 Literature Review

The particle transport characteristics for eight kinds of barriers, usually seen in the near road area, are studied under various meteorological conditions.[3] The last two decades have seen constant growth in information and communication technologies whose applications have transformed the operation and management of businesses in different sectors including the transport and logistics sector[1]. According to X. Jin, L. Yang, X. Du, and Y. Yang The airborne particles emitted from vehicles will jeopardize human health, causing the diseases such as lung cancer, cardiovascular disease and asthma[3]. According to A. Comi and A. Nuzzolo, Information and communication technologies (ICT) are enhancing supply chain performance with improved efficiency and responsiveness The Supply Chain (SC) performance is significantly boosted with the use of electronic portable devices[2]. For the development of better traffic and to understand RTO system we need a software project that guide us about the project.

1.3 Present System

Currently RTO system is digitalize but to need internal details about RTO and RTO test. Existing system is very complex & many more Real-life problem. Many employees are needed to handle current system.It is more expensive process. Immediate responses to the queries are difficult. Lots of times are consumed for each report generation. We require to build new

Website according to RTO office infrastructure and Facilities. So that all the people can get information about the e-RTO.

1.4 Proposed system

For the development of E-RTO system we are using here ASP.net and to store data we are using SQL Server 2008. It makes possible to make online RTO system, so we can understand all the internal process of RTO and also get many information about different types of license. We can also go through the mock test which is needed to take license from RTO.

1.4.1 Snap Shot of a Project

Some snap shots of a project are:

Fig: Admin Login

Fig: Admin-Check Registration

Fig: Admin-Enter Test

Fig: User-Home Page RTO

Fig: User-RTO Mock Test

Fig:User- Forget Password

Fig: User Registration

2. Methodology

2.1 Asp.Net

ASP.NET 3.5 and Visual Studio 2008 bring great new functionality around Web development and design that makes building standards based, next generation Web sites easier than ever. From the inclusion of ASP.NET AJAX into the runtime, to new controls, the new LINQ data capabilities, to improved support for CSS, JavaScript and others, Web development has taken a significant step forward.

Source: <https://www.asp.net/downloads/vs2008>

2.2 Microsoft SQL Server 2005

Microsoft SQL Server 2005 Express Edition has been designed with older Microsoft operating systems in mind. Offering bespoke data management options as well as the ability to enhance levels of performance, this bundle can be downloaded in the event that the original SQL copy was lost or otherwise corrupted. This is the official software package offered by Microsoft. Originally published in 2005, Microsoft SQL Server 2005 Express Edition provides the user with all of the most important tools to better manage his or her system. As the name may already suggest, this bundle can be used with older versions of Microsoft such as Microsoft XP and Microsoft 2000. Some core processes include advanced data protection, the better management of online applications and superior data storage solutions. This software can come in quite handy if a system seems to be running poorly.

Source: <https://microsoft-sql-server-2005-express-edition.en.softonic.com/#app-softonic-review>

2.3 HTML

HTML (Hypertext Markup Language) is the set of markup symbols or codes inserted in a file intended for display on a World Wide Web browser page. The markup tells the Web browser how to display a Web page's words and images for the user. Each individual markup code is

referred to as an element (but many people also refer to it as a tag). Some elements come in pairs that indicate when some display effect is to begin and when it is to end.

Source: <https://searchmicroservices.techtarget.com>

2.4 CSS

CSS stands for "Cascading Style Sheet." Cascading style sheets are used to format the layout of Web pages. They can be used to define text styles, table sizes, and other aspects of Web pages that previously could only be defined in a page's HTML.

CSS helps Web developers create a uniform look across several pages of a Web site. Instead of defining the style of each table and each block of text within a page's HTML, commonly used styles need to be defined only once in a CSS document.

Source: <https://techterms.com/definition/css>

2.5 Feasibility Study

A feasibility study is an analysis of how successfully a project can be completed, accounting for factors that affect it such as economic, technological, legal and scheduling factors. Project managers use feasibility studies to determine potential positive and negative outcomes of a project before investing a considerable amount of time and money into it.

Source: <https://www.investopedia.com/terms/f/feasibility-study.asp>

Result

By using this system we can get Information about RTO and another information like Driving License, Learning License and all the RTO service online. This system helps to solve the time related problem. System helps customer to find his/her requirement in various RTO Information online. It also Provide Online RTO tests.

Conclusion

In today's world with the increasing traffic and longer commuting distances it is

becoming very difficult for people to travel for their particular licenses issue. Also most of the people today work for longer hours and do not have the flexibility to take a break from work to give the licenses tests. People have not spent more time for licenses test. The People want a facility where they can have easy to issue their licenses. The facility to achieve schedule date by SMS, call or mail. The people collect their license from post and travel from long distance for issuing license. So, the people waste their money. We like this opportunity to convey our special thanks to all those who played role in making this project a success and a great learning experience for us. So we are conclude that this system helps people to understand RTO system and also the traffic rules.

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